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“SWEEPERS FOR SPACE”

They sweep the streets while victims weep,
Is this how they return what they cut deep?

Where there are thousands inside bars,
Are they exempt and just picking dirty jars?

They are outside, so they reform,
If I am a victim, I don't want it to be the norm.
They acted ruthlessly in this already cruel world,
But who are we to get a stone to hurl?

Outside bars, they pay the price,
To ease jail congestion and sleep nice.
Is this a genuine rehab and reform?
Or just a lighter penalty for those who can afford?